

The Association of Serum Zinc and Magnesium Status with Acne Vulgaris Severity: A Case-Control Study

Varun Kohir¹, Manjunath Durgappa², Ramya B. G.³, Shwetha Sawant⁴

¹Senior Resident, Department of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology, Navodaya Medical College Hospital and Research Centre. Raichur- 584103, Karnataka, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Medical Gastroenterology. Rajiv Gandhi Super-speciality hospital (OPEC). Raichur Institute of Medical Sciences. Raichur- 584102, Karnataka, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology, Navodaya Medical College Hospital and Research Centre. Raichur- 584103, Karnataka, India

⁴Associate Professor, Department of Ear, Nose and Throat, Navodaya Medical College Hospital and Research Centre. Raichur- 584103, Karnataka, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Ramya B. G.

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Abstract:

Introduction: Acne vulgaris is a chronic disorder of pilosebaceous unit which commonly occurs between ages of 11 – 30 years. The aetiology of acne is multifactorial. Trace elements like zinc (Zn) and magnesium (Mg) play important roles in various biochemical processes in the body and thus may have role in pathogenesis of acne vulgaris. Hence, we aimed to assess serum Zn and Mg levels and to correlate same with severity in acne.

Materials and Methods: A total 50 cases and 50 controls aged 18-45 years who visiting our hospital during march 2021 to march 2023 were included and blood samples were collected to quantify serum zinc (Zn) and magnesium (Mg) levels using a flame atomic spectrometer, a susceptible analytical technique.

Results: The study population exhibited a sex ratio of 1:1, with mean age of 28.10 years for cases and 29.39 years for controls. The average serum Zn concentrations were 93.80±28.56 µg/dl for cases, 98.33±33.88 µg/dl for controls and Mg concentrations were 1.94±0.18 mg/dl for cases, 1.98±0.17 mg/dl for controls respectively with no significant differences in serum levels were found between individuals with and without acne. However, a moderate correlation was observed between acne severity and Zn levels (“p-value” 0.089), suggesting a potential association.

Conclusion: The study found no significant correlation between serum zinc and magnesium levels and acne incidence. However, a plausible association was observed between acne severity and serum zinc levels, suggesting a potential dependence of the former on the latter.

Keywords: Zinc, Magnesium, Acne Vulgaris.

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Introduction

Acne vulgaris affect 9.4% of the global population and eighth most prevalent disease irrespective of gender or race [1,2]. Acne can cause psychological impact on the person affecting quality of life [3-5]. There are many causes for acne, one of them is the excess production of growth and reproductive hormones [6,7].

Also, there is evidence of serum insulin growth factor-1 to determine occurrence of acne [8]. Trace elements like zinc (Zn) and magnesium (Mg) regulate production of these hormones and exhibit an anti-inflammatory action [9-14]. But these correlation is bit varied and there is paucity of research data regarding the role of Mg and Zn in the pathogenesis and severity of acne. Hence, this study was under taken to address and investigate role of

these elements in relation to occurrence of acne and its severity. Zinc is an important micronutrient which control gene transcription and the metabolism of lipids, proteins and nucleic acids. Zinc also plays a critical role in maintaining healthy immune function, wound healing, and reproductive function. It blocks keratinocytes from expressing integrins and lowers the levels of inflammatory mediators like nitric oxide. It has antiandrogenic properties [15-17]. There are various studies in literature showing varied association to no association between serum Zn levels and acne, its severity and role of Zn in its treatment [9,18-21].

Magnesium is the second most abundant intracellular element that regulates diverse biochemical reaction with normal range of serum

Mg is 1.7-2.6 mg/dl. Tamara A et al. found a significant difference between serum Mg levels and severity of acne vulgaris ($p=0.032$) with a positive correlation. However, Mg levels were still within normal range [22]. In a study by Ricardo, dietary supplementation of Mg was prescribed to acne patients with 100% of patients reported complete regression suggesting a possible correlation [23]. Though there is varied association between zinc and acne in studies done so far, there is paucity of data regarding role of magnesium in acne vulgaris, hence the present study was taken up.

Materials and Methodology

A case-control study with a ratio of 1:1 i.e. same sample size for acne cases and controls was conducted. Sample size, "n" was calculated by using the following standard formula for sample size calculation [1].

Objectives

1. To assess serum Zn and serum Mg levels in patients with acne
2. To correlate serum Zn and serum Mg levels with severity of acne

Further, the male to female ratio was 1:1 to include proportionate gender representation. Patients with acne grade 2 (Fig.1) and above, between 18-45 years, willing to give consent was included. Patients having lesions other than acne vulgaris were excluded. Remaining 50 were selected at random as controls with age and sex match and were examined and the grade of acne was evaluated based on table 1.

Patients were investigated further and serum levels of Zn and Mg were found out using blood samples. Correlation between serum levels of Zn and Mg and prevalence with severity of acne were investigated using statistical methods and tools.

Results

A total of 100 samples with a male to female ratio of 1:1 were selected 25 cases and 25 controls among both. The mean age of female cases and male cases were 28.04 ± 6.27 years and 28.16 ± 8.80 years with an overall mean age of cases at 28.10 ± 7.56 years corroborating with fact that the incidence of acne is more in the age group of 20-30 years.

The samples were categorized into seven groups based on the age. Gender wise age distribution

showed peak in incidence between 20-30 years age as shown in table 2. Study found 9(18.0%) and 1(2.0%) of the cases, 5(10.0%) and 1(2.0%) of controls had lower zinc level and higher Zn level than normal serum Zn levels respectively summing upto 14(14.0%) of 100 samples had lower and 2 (2.0%) had higher Zn level. The mean serum zinc values of cases and controls were $93.8 \mu\text{g/dl} \pm 28.56 \mu\text{g/dl}$ and $98.33 \mu\text{g/dl} \pm 33.88 \mu\text{g/dl}$, respectively. The "p-value" (Table 3) for association of acne with serum zinc in all cases and controls was not significant. Similar results were obtained for female as well as male groups. Independently zinc levels in case and controls had similar distribution.

The mean value of zinc in grade 2 acne (fig.1) was higher ($96.35 \pm 29.32 \mu\text{g/dl}$) than in grade 3 (fig.2) ($75.1 \pm 11.06 \mu\text{g/dl}$) ("p-value" - 0.089). Similarly, the mean values of Mg levels in grade 2 and grade 3 acne were $1.95 \pm 0.18 \text{ mg/dl}$ and $1.84 \pm 0.16 \text{ mg/dl}$, respectively ("p-value"- 0.152). Serum magnesium level in cases and controls was assessed which showed 2.0% and 4.0% cases had lower Mg level and higher Mg level than normal range ($1.7-2.2 \text{ mg/dl}$) respectively. All controls had within the range serum Mg levels. A total of 1.0% samples had lower and 2.0% had higher Mg level. Mean Mg levels for cases and controls were $1.94 \text{ mg/dl} \pm 0.18 \text{ mg/dl}$ and $1.98 \text{ mg/dl} \pm 0.17 \text{ mg/dl}$, respectively. The mean value of serum Mg of cases was lower than controls. The "p-value" was 0.220 (>0.05) which was statistically not significant implying that there is no correlation between occurrence of acne and serum Mg level. Similar results were obtained for female as well as male groups, independently.

The mean values of Zn levels in grade 2 and grade 3 acne were $96.35 \pm 29.32 \mu\text{g/dl}$ and $75.1 \pm 11.06 \mu\text{g/dl}$, respectively and the mean values of Mg levels in grade 2 and grade 3 acne were $1.95 \pm 0.18 \text{ mg/dl}$ and $1.84 \pm 0.16 \text{ mg/dl}$ respectively for which too, p-values were not significant.

However "p-value" of serum Zn level was nearer to 0.05, which was statistically not quite insignificant implying that there is an element of dependency of serum Zn level on grade of acne (i.e. higher the grade of the acne, lower is the Zn level). Out of 50 cases 9 cases (18.0%) and 1 case (2.0%) had lower zinc and Mg levels and 1 case (2.0%) and 2 cases (4.0%) had higher Zn and Mg levels, respectively. serum Zn and Mg levels were lower in grade 3 acne cases than in grade 2 acne cases.

Table 1: Acne grading system

Grade 1 acne (mild acne)	Comedones and occasional papules
Grade 2 acne (Moderate acne)	Comedones, papules and few pustules
Grade 3 acne (Severe acne)	Predominant pustules, nodules and abscesses
Grade 4 acne (Cystic acne)	Mainly pseudocysts, abscesses and scarring

Table 2: Groups based on age

Age Groups→	<20 Yrs	20 -24 Yrs	25-29 Yrs	30-34 Yrs	35-39 Yrs	40-44 Yrs	≥45 Yrs	All
Female	5	10	12	11	6	1	5	50
Male	3	21	10	7	7	1	1	50
Total	8	31	22	18	13	2	6	100

Table 3: Serum zinc levels in cases and controls

Summary of serum Zn Profile		cases	Controls	All	“p-value”*
Female	Mean value	101.68	100.48	101.08	0.904
	Std. Dev.	32.18	37.42	34.55	
	Range	62-211	67.2-245	62-245	
Male	Mean value	85.93	96.19	91.06	0.182
	Std. Dev	22.37	30.55	27.00	
	Range	55-163	43.14-153.5	43.14-163	
All cases and controls	Mean value	93.80	98.33	96.07	0.472
	Std. Dev	28.56	33.88	31.26	
	Range	55-211	43.14-245	43.14-245	

*Unpaired two tailed homoscedastic t-test, and ANOVA test, statistically not significant if “p-value” >0.05.

Table 4: Serum magnesium level profile and p-values

Summary of serum Mg Profile		Cases	Controls	All	“p-value”*
Female	Mean value	1.93	1.95	1.94	0.704
	Std. Dev.	0.20	0.17	0.18	
	Range	1.69-2.3	1.7-2.2	1.69-2.2	
Male	Mean value	1.94	2.01	1.98	0.162
	Std. Dev	0.17	0.16	0.17	
	Range	1.71-2.2	1.7-2.2	1.7-2.2	
All cases and controls	Mean value	1.94	1.98	1.96	0.220
	Std. Dev	0.18	0.17	0.17	
	Range	1.69-2.3	1.7-2.2	1.69-2.3	

*Unpaired two tailed homoscedastic t-test, and ANOVA, Statistically not significant if “p-value” >0.05

Figure 1: Sample female case of grade 2 acne

Figure 2: Sample male case of grade 3 acne

Discussion

The essential trace elements, micro-nutrients and vitamins play important roles in diverse biochemical reactions of the body. Although there are sufficient studies conducted so far, studies do not have a conclusive evidence to relate serum level with occurrence or severity of acne.

Our aim was to assess role of serum Zn and Mg levels with acne and its severity. Acne cases are highest between the ages of 20 to 35 years, which is 80%, similar finding was reported earlier by Rademaker et al., Epstein E. and Collier CN et al. [24-26]. Serum zinc level range is (reference interval) from 70 to 180 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ (mean value of $120 \pm 22 \mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$). The normal range for serum Mg level is 1.7 to 2.2 mg/dl (0.85 to 1.10 mmol/L). In the present study, mean values of serum Zn were lower than the mean serum zinc levels of controls. The statistical correlation result of Zn level with presence of acne was not significant ("p-value"-0.472).

The study by Satish Chandra of 50 cases and 50 controls reported mean serum Zn levels were 83.12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ and 84.68 $\mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ respectively and concluded with statistically non-significant results [11]. Saleh OB et al. reported mean serum values of Zn level in

cases and controls as $95.67 \pm 4.58 \mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ and $102.42 \pm 18.10 \mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$, respectively [9]. In a study on Iranian patients (100 cases and 100 controls) by Rostami MM et al., mean serum level of Zn in acne patients and controls was $81.31 \pm 17.63 \mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ and $82.63 \pm 17.49 \mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$, respectively with statistically non-significant results [14]. These studies are almost in accordance with the findings of the present study conducted. All the investigators reported lower serum Zn level in cases than in controls which is similar to the observations of our study. Further the previous investigations found correlation between Zn level and occurrence of acne as statistically not significant which concurred with the findings of the present study. However, the all-female case and control study under taken by Alhassan TMMO, reported a contrasting finding with respect to the present study [12].

In another study by Butool F. et al. Study, mean serum zinc levels in patients was 24.4 ± 2.4 whereas the levels in controls was 99.4 ± 4.5 with a statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) result [21]. The mean value of zinc in grade 2 acne was $96.35 \pm 29.32 \mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$ and in grade 3 acne cases in our study was $75.1 \pm 11.06 \mu\text{g}/\text{dl}$. The zinc levels were lower in grade 3 acne as compared to Zn levels in grade 2 acne. The result was statistically not quite insignificant (p -value

0.089), which implies ample possibility of correlation between Zn level and severity of acne. The present study result is similar to observation reported by Satish Chandra (mean serum Zn levels among the patients with mild, moderate and severe acne were 89.23 µg/dL, 79.12 µg/dL and 72.36 µg/dL respectively) [11]. However, Praneeth KG and Priscilla T reported no correlation between serum Zn level and severity of acne [27]. Ahmed LH et al, reported no correlation, though serum Zn levels in patients with acne vulgaris, especially those with severe form of the disease were lower, which is in accordance with the present study [28]. Mean Mg levels of cases and controls of the present study were 1.94±0.18 mg/dl and 1.98±0.17 mg/dl, respectively. The result was statistically not significant ("p-value" -0.220) implying no correlation between magnesium level and occurrence of acne.

Case and control study by Saleh B et al. observed that Mg levels (controls 1.14±0.17 mg/dl and cases ranged from 1.13±0.20mg/dl in severe acne to 1.29±0.18 in mild acne) were related to severity of acne [9]. Tamara A. et al., reported positive correlation of magnesium with severity of acne [30]. In another clinical study of 32 female patients, Jaripur M. et al. reported improved QoL (quality of life) after Mg supplements however, authors did not explicitly report serum level measurements in favour of Mg level dependence on acne [31]. These studies contrast the statistically non-significant result of the present study, which may be due to lower Mg reference levels, mean ages, ethnic or genetic differences.

Conclusion

Acne vulgaris is a chronic inflammatory disease of the pilosebaceous unit. It is most predominant in adolescence and its occurrence and severity can be related to serum Zn and Mg levels but in our study we conclude that there is no significant association between occurrence and severity of acne with serum Zn and Mg levels. But large scale studies are further needed to arrive at a definite conclusion.

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